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Using Mission Analysis Software GMAT to develop skills in Astrodynamics

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ABSTRACT

Learning about the geometry and kinematics of orbital motion (or ‘astrodynamics’) is challenging due to its 3D nature. To address this, the University of Bristol have developed 3D orbit visualization exercises using a free NASA tool called ‘General Mission Analysis Tool’ (GMAT). The aims are to develop skills in manipulation of orbits and to focus on areas subject to common misconceptions. The skills targeted include: varying orbital elements and observing the effect, interpreting ground tracks, exploring features of sun-synchronous, Molniya and geostationary orbits, adding pro and retrograde burns and seeing the effects, performing inclination changes and Hohmann transfers. Common misconceptions include: confusing the orbital elements, thinking that satellites move faster in their orbits with increasing altitude, thinking that geostationary satellites are not moving (relative to stars), forgetting that Earth rotates when considering ground tracks, thinking that a Hohmann transfer is composed of one burn only, thinking that for a chaser spacecraft to catch up with a target in orbit, it must accelerate. Feedback from students is discussed, along with proposals for further work to assess the extent to which misconceptions have been addressed. Overall, GMAT exercises offer a promising way to visualise orbits and improve conceptual understanding of astrodynamics.

Keywords: orbit modelling, 3D visualization, astrodynamics, GMAT

INTRODUCTION

To understand the movement of spacecraft and the paths that they take around planets, students studying physics and aerospace engineering learn about the

geometry and kinematics of bodies and their trajectories through space. This area is called 'celestial mechanics' or 'astrodynamics' or sometimes 'mission analysis' and it is one of the most challenging parts of such a course, due to the 3D nature of the learning. There are many excellent texts in this area to provide a strong theoretical grounding [1–3]. But 2D diagrams and descriptions in texts cannot fully describe the 3D motion of bodies through space. In exams and tests before this work commenced, students at the University of Bristol regularly showed evidence of misunderstandings and a failure to engage with astrodynamics. It was thought, therefore, to be an area very suited to the application of 3D visualisation and simulation tools. There is evidence from previous studies that simulation-based learning can potentially enhance motivation as well as enhancing understanding [4].

Fortunately, there are now several tools available, including 'General Mission Analysis Tool' (GMAT), 'Systems Tool Kit' (STK), 'Orekit', 'Freeflyer' etc. to build models of and permit the visualisation of spacecraft astrodynamics. These are based on numerical solution of the equations of motion and enable users to manipulate the views of the path of the spacecraft. It has already been shown that "user ability to handle technology in order to move around between different representations of mathematical or physical objects promotes conceptual growth" [5].

Previous authors have already looked at a number of specific examples of the use of these tools, including orbital elements, geostationary eclipse season, launch windows, reference frames, lighting, attitude, formation flying and manoeuvres [6]. Others have used them to reinforce satellite communications engineering concepts [7]. In other work, it has been maintained that the introduction of these tools at the expense of student exposure to the analytical basics of astrodynamics may lead to a reliance on simulation, instead of analysis, to solve problems [8]. These recommendations will be followed in this work.

Many research studies have demonstrated that "conceptions" are often highly resistant to traditional instruction, and despite passing examinations, students can still hold "misconceptions" that are at variance with formal science ideas [9]. Therefore, in this work, the aim was to improve student learning in astrodynamics through simulations which develop specific skills and address specific misconceptions. The simulation exercises were based on already established principles for effective simulation-based learning [10].

In section 1, the content of the astrodynamics aspects of the Aerospace Engineering degree at the University of Bristol is described, along with the most frequent misunderstandings and gaps in knowledge in the course and the choice of the astrodynamics tool. In section 2, examples of the exercises are presented. The feedback on the simulations and the limitations of this work are covered in the discussion in section 4. In section 5, further work is proposed and the conclusions follow in section 6.

1 METHODOLOGY

1.1 Content of Astrodynamics of Space Systems course

The University of Bristol has delivered a Space Systems course module as part of the 4-year Aerospace Engineering 'Integrated Masters' degree (Bachelor and Masters rolled in to one course) for many years. It is a compulsory course unit in the second year of Aerospace Engineering and is optional for students from the Engineering Design course. Cohorts are typically 120-130 students. It is worth 10 credits out of 120

credits for the year and currently comprises 24 hours lectures and 6 hours of computer simulation classes. Of the 24 hrs of lectures, 7 hours are used to cover a theoretical introduction to orbits, including: Kepler's and Newton's laws (and proving Kepler's laws from Newton); conic sections; 3D reference systems; orbital elements; ground tracks and different types of orbits; 2-body motion; The Kepler equation and the vis-viva equation; out of plane manoeuvres; Hohmann transfers; basic rendezvous principles.

1.2 Common misconceptions

In this course, the theoretical background of introductory astrodynamics is presented in standard lecture format. Before the simulations were developed, in end of year exams, coursework and mid-course tests, students regularly showed evidence of misunderstandings and a failure to engage with astrodynamics. Many able students avoided optional astrodynamics questions in exams and exhibited gaps in understanding. To address this, a list of desired skills and some of the most common misconceptions in introductory astrodynamics was assembled from systematically reviewing past exams and coursework (*Tables 1 and 2*).

Table 1. Basic skills required in introductory astrodynamics

No.	Skills
1	Varying orbital elements and observing the effects
2	Interpreting ground tracks
3	Exploring features of Sun-synchronous, Molniya and Geostationary orbits
4	Adding pro and retrograde burns and seeing the effects
5	Performing inclination changes
6	Performing Hohmann transfers

Table 2. Examples of common misconceptions in introductory astrodynamics

No.	Misconception
1	Confusing the orbital elements
2	Thinking that satellites move faster in their orbits with increasing altitude
3	Thinking that Geostationary satellites are not moving (relative to stars)
4	Forgetting that Earth rotates when considering ground tracks
5	Thinking that a Hohmann transfer is composed of one burn only
6	Thinking that for a chaser spacecraft to catch up with a target in orbit, it must accelerate in the same orbit.

1.3 Choice of Tool

There are now a wide variety of tools available for performing mission analysis and astrodynamics. The University of BRISTOL started out in 2011 using STK by AGI. When STK provider in Europe started charging for licences, another tool was required. The criteria for selection included: scientific credibility, ability to perform Low Earth Orbit, interplanetary, low energy and constellation missions, user support, documentation and a low licence fee. Based on these criteria, a free tool developed by

NASA Goddard Space Flight Center: 'General Mission Analysis Tool' (GMAT) was selected [11]. It has been extensively tested and verified and has been used for more than 9 NASA missions [12]. The system can display trajectories in space, plot parameters against one another, and save parameters to files for later processing. The trajectory and plot capabilities are fully interactive, plotting data as a mission is run and allowing users to zoom into regions of interest. Trajectories and data can be viewed in any defined coordinate system, and GMAT allows users to rotate the view and set the focus to any object in the display [11].

2 EXERCISES

2.1 Instructions

A set of step-by-step instructions through the exercises and tool menus was developed by the authors. These instructions also include explanations of the different commands and interfaces. The students are also required to answer questions as they progress through the exercises. It is worth noting that some excellent tutorials are provided by the GMAT developers, but they are aimed at allowing users to become familiar with the software itself, not at explaining or helping students to better understand astrodynamics theory. The students undertake these simulations during 3 computer laboratory classes of 2hrs each, just after the theoretical lectures. If the students do not complete the exercises during class time, they are asked to finish them in their own time. Although voluntary, these classes are attended at 90-95%. Staff and teaching assistants are available during the class to answer all questions. The worksheet questions are aimed at inspiring the student to explore and question what they see, e.g.: "*Sat01 has completed a complete orbit, as it starts and finishes at the periapsis, but there is a gap in the ground track on the plot. Why?*" The following sections describe the exercises covered in the instructions and their rationale.

2.2 Orbital elements

Textbooks on astrodynamics will usually list and define each of the 6 orbital elements (semi-major axis, eccentricity, inclination, right ascension of the ascending node, argument of periapsis and true anomaly are used here), with the aid of a labelled diagram. Understanding of the elements requires some spatial imaging skills and without practice many students do not understand them fully after learning the theory in class. To help students to explore these elements, 3 satellites are modelled with identical orbital elements. Then one element, e.g.: inclination, is varied for each of the 3 orbits so that the students can simultaneously see 3 orbits with 3 different inclinations. This 3D visualisation allows them to see how different values for the elements affect their orbits. The ability to zoom, pan and view the orbit from different angles makes it easier to see how the orientation of the orbit has changed. The students compare and explore the different elements one by one. This exercise addresses both the skills No. 1 and misconception No. 1 and 2 in *Tables 1 and 2*.

2.3 Ground Tracks

To address skills No. 2 and misconception No.4, an exercise on ground tracks is provided. Ground tracks are given as 2D plots based on a map of the Earth. It is challenging for beginners to understand even the simplest ground tracks, such as the sinusoidal pattern of an inclined circular orbit. Interpreting ground tracks is a skill which takes practice. Ground tracks can take on unexpected forms, such as loops, but the

cause of these forms becomes clearer when they can be matched with the 3D view of the spacecraft orbiting above the rotating body. At the beginning of the laboratory a demonstration script shows 3 types of orbits with their matching ground tracks for the students to explore. The students are asked to compare the ground track with the orbit, to see how they link. For example, they are asked to work out the inclination of an orbit from the ground track plot only and then to look at the 3D orbit.

2.4 Special orbits

The selection of a satellite's orbit is driven by the mission it is required to perform, whether science, Earth observation or communications. A few orbits are particularly interesting for their features. They are: geostationary, sun-synchronous and Molniya orbits. To address skills No.3 and misconception No.3, the students are required to set these orbits up as simulations and are then asked to work out why they might be useful from their ground tracks and elements.

2.5 Pro and Retrograde burns and their effects

A prograde burn is a firing of the spacecraft main thruster in the direction opposite to the direction of travel, a retrograde burn is a firing in the direction of travel. To develop skill No. 4, students experiment with adding pro and retrograde burns to orbits. For rendezvous between a target spacecraft and a chaser spacecraft, if the target is travelling ahead of the chaser, then the chaser needs to drop into a lower orbit to allow it to catch up. In a demonstration simulation provided to the students, they can see how a chaser Soyuz performs 2 retrograde burns to drop into the lower altitude orbit and then 2 prograde burns to return to the target's altitude (see *Figure 1*). This is counterintuitive. Misconception No. 6 is to believe that performing a greater prograde burn (or '*flooring it*', according to one student) will help the chaser spacecraft catch up to the target spacecraft, whereas it will just raise the apoapsis of the orbit. Many students are startled to see this effect in practice and need to see the evidence both in 3D and in a graph of velocity and time, such as in *Figure 1*.

Fig. 1. A GMAT graph of the velocity of a Soyuz spacecraft as it performs a rendezvous with the International Space Station.

2.6 Inclination manoeuvres

An inclination manoeuvre is also called an 'out of plane' manoeuvre as it causes the orbital plane to change by changing its angle of inclination. Depending on the change of angle of inclination, it can be expensive on fuel and thus it is important that all such burns are considered carefully. To address skill No. 5, students investigate inclination burns, which are burns at an angle to the direction of travel. First, they perform theoretical calculations to work out the value of the burn elements, then they add the burn in to the simulation. They can then compare theoretical and model results.

2.7 Hohmann transfers

A Hohmann transfer is the most efficient way, in terms of fuel, to change the altitude of a circular orbit [2]. It is required skill No. 6. It involves two burns, the first to raise the apoapsis to the altitude of the desired orbit, followed by the second to circularise the new orbit. The students initially calculate the theoretical values of the two burns using standard theory. Students frequently forget the second burn (misconception No. 5). However, by seeing the result of modelling without a second burn, the students realise the necessity of two burns. They know from the instructions and the lectures that the finished mission should look like a version of *Fig. 2*. The students are also then asked to compare their theoretical results with the model results and to explain the difference.

Fig. 2. The finished GMAT Hohmann transfer exercise

3 FEEDBACK

In 2015-16, at the end of the unit, students were requested to complete an anonymous feedback form on paper. In this they were asked: "Rate each element of the course out of 10, including individual lecturers, the materials and the coursework". 54 students completed the feedback out of a cohort of 134. Of these, 90% rated the simulation exercises 7 or more out of 10. The students were also asked "How did the GMAT labs help you in your learning, if at all?" The responses included 26 variations on: "Helped me to understand concepts that were hard to visualise". They also included helping

them to understand orbital elements and Hohmann transfer. Three mentioned that *“It was quite fun and we all know that playing is the best way to learn”*! One pointed out: *“It helped having staff to ask questions to”*. But also, negative ones included: *“I didn’t find them that helpful. There were no clear instructions for how to do a Hohmann transfer, this was left for you to work out, which was hard”*. Two people suggested: *“Maybe a longer lab time slot would give more time to understand what you are doing and what the results show”*.

4 DISCUSSION

When setting the exercises, it was considered whether to set them in MATLAB, as this offers the familiarity of a known tool together with the satisfaction of developing the orbits from first principles via a numerical solution of the equations of motion. However, from a learning point of view, it was considered more important to have the 3D visualisation aspects provided by the GUI of the GMAT software. However, it is then a challenge to achieve a balance between helping the students to learn a new software and helping them to gain the desired skills. Another limitation of the exercises described here is that they are not open-ended, which is a desirable feature of simulation work [10]. It is challenging to provide sufficient support for open-ended exercises with cohorts of 130, but this is certainly a goal for future work. The ultimate question is whether the introduction of these simulation exercises has made any difference to student learning and understanding. It is difficult to assess this without conducting an experiment with parallel classes and comparing directly. But tests after the simulation based learning and the introduction of a compulsory astrodynamics question in the exam have aided in the assessment. Results in tests have shown an improvement in understanding of orbital elements and Hohmann transfers – a detailed discussion of this is beyond the scope of this paper. The feedback questionnaire indicates that the students find the exercises helpful although some students wished for more time in the class.

5 FURTHER WORK

As mentioned in the discussion and by the students, it would be desirable to reduce the scope of the exercises or increase the length of the class. One way of comparing student’s understanding before and after the simulation exercises is by using “concept inventories”. These are questionnaires put together by experts which can be used to probe students’ understanding of scientific phenomena. The most well-known of these inventories is the force concept inventory [13]. It is proposed to develop a concept inventory of introductory astrodynamics concepts with a collection of experts via the Space Universities Network – a network of UK Space science and engineering University teaching staff. Analysis of the results of administering such a questionnaire could lead to a better understanding as to how effective the 3D exercises are.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the NASA 3D mission analysis simulation tool ‘GMAT’ has been used to develop important skills and to address common misconceptions in the field of astrodynamics. A series of exercises using GMAT have been developed to cover orbital elements, ground tracks, special orbits, Hohmann transfers, prograde, retrograde and inclination burns. Feedback from students indicates that they have found it rewarding and feel that their conceptual understanding appears to have

improved. Further concept inventory work would enable rigorous testing to see if misconceptions have been addressed.

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